

ON THE CATEGORIES OF OBJECTIVITY AND SUBJECTIVITY IN LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12785379>

Abstract. *The study highlights the influence of anthropocentric linguistics, which focuses on the relationship between extralinguistic factors and language. By integrating philosophical and epistemological perspectives, the research addresses the necessity, purpose, and creation of subjective semantic relationships to meet communicative needs. The discussion includes the contributions of Wilhelm von Humboldt on the subjective perception of objects and its reflection in language. The article explores how linguistic categories of subject and object express logical and grammatical distinctions and how evaluative attitudes manifest in communication. It concludes by emphasizing the importance of syntactic and semantic methods in expressing subjective attitudes and evaluative relations in language.*

Keywords: *objectivity, subjectivity, cognitive linguistics, subject category, semantic relationships, evaluative attitude, syntactic method, anthropocentric linguistics, paradigmatic relations, syntagmatic relations.*

INTRODUCTION

In linguistics, semantic, structural, functional, uniqueness-universality features of the semantics of subjective relation have been studied to a certain extent. The ontological nature of this category, in particular, the presence of these semantics at different linguistic levels and their status in paradigmatic, syntagmatic, and hierarchical relations, was given a certain amount of attention. Anthropocentric linguistics, which began to form within the framework of linguistics from the second half of the 20th century and now occupies a leading position, now focuses on the issues of the relationship of extralinguistic factors (such as the speaker/listener, speech conditions) to language. Cognitive Linguistics has emerged as a prominent field in the study of language and its cognitive underpinnings. One key aspect of this approach is the emphasis on the role of the subject category in understanding language use and structure. Cognitive linguists argue that the subject category is not merely a formal grammatical construct, but rather a conceptual category that is grounded in human cognition and experience. As a result, issues such as the necessity and purpose of the semantics of the subjective relationship, why it has such a multi-level system, and how such semantic relationships are created to satisfy communicative needs are gaining relevance. This research is valuable because it solves this important problem.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

It is known that any special science develops on the basis of philosophy, logic, methodology and methods of leading natural sciences. The theory of knowledge (epistemology) teaches that any private science owner of philosophy and logic is the unity and struggle of opposites, the transition of quantitative changes to qualitative changes. Because these laws and their categories are manifested in each subject of science in its own way (inherently dependent on its own reality).

The problems of objectivity and subjectivity belong to the group of epistemological issues, which are primarily solved within the framework of philosophical sciences. This problem is related

to the foundations of worldview, not only with the nature of consciousness, but also with the relationship between consciousness and lifestyle, which is one of the main issues of philosophy, and therefore is of great importance for all concrete sciences, in particular, for humanities and, above all, for linguistics and arouses interest. Linguistics cannot ignore the issue of the relationship between consciousness and existence, because any explanation of language is directed to the description of its content, that is, to its cognitive-communicative function in society.

RESEARCH AND DISCUSSION

Wilhelm von Humboldt, one of the founders of the science of theoretical linguistics, emphasized that the perception of objects is subjective and that this subjectivity is reflected in the construction of language. Taking into account that any objective perception is accompanied by subjectivity, "any individual person, even without paying attention to the language, should be considered as having a special point of view in the perception of the world." Therefore, a person expresses his subjective attitude to objective reality, and the speaker's positive or negative attitude to reality is reflected in language using linguistic and extralinguistic means.

The terms subject and object are used in linguistics to express logical and grammatical categories. In the language, the object acts as a complement, and the subject acts as a possessor. The problems of objectivity and subjectivity in language directly go back to the ideas of V. Humboldt. Ideas about subjectivity appear in linguistic theories in different forms. In particular, these concepts are important in the directions of stylistics, first of all, in expressing subtleties of meaning and emotional evaluation. The words evaluation and attitude are closely related to each other, and in linguistics, the terms "evaluative attitude", "subjective attitude", "positive attitude", "negative attitude" are widely used by linguists. Here, it is worth noting that interpersonal relations arise through evaluation, that is, the participants of the dialogue express their opinion in the process of communication based on their personal assessment of themselves and the listener. In turn, the assessment is formed on the basis of the relations of communicants in communication and is reflected openly or secretly in the process of mutual exchange of ideas. Therefore, the term "valuation attitude" means the subjective attitude towards reality, and the evaluation attitude emerges in speech through language level units. The positive and negative meaning of the language level means is the main place in the expression of the value attitude.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, at the syntactic level, the syntactic-semantic method has a special place and is of great importance in the expression of subjective attitude, because the content of any sentence consists of the relationship of ductal and modal meanings. It is necessary to pay special attention to the issue of object and subject in the expression of the evaluation in a syntactic way, and on this basis, it is necessary to analyze the occurrence of the evaluation in a semantic syntactic manner. In these processes, it is necessary to assume that the positive or negative evaluation of the relationship expressed in the sentence occurs explicitly or implicitly. In both cases, the sentence acts as a means of expression.

If the sentence is a means of expressing the value relationship as a whole, it is called open expression - syntactic method. If the value relationship in the sentence is hidden, it is called - syntactic-semantic method. In English language, the relation of value appears in the sentence through exhortations, word repetitions, inversion, emphasis, sarcasm, as well as words that mean the relation of lexical value.

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